

CHEMISTRY

COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE EFFECT OF INDIVIDUAL AND MIXED ETAMON AND ZINC SULFATE ON THE ACTIVITY OF CORN ROOT MERISTEM CELLS

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Abstract

The paper presents the results of studies of the mitotic activity of root meristem cells of corn seedlings (Sterling) under the simultaneous influence of the drug Etamon and increasing concentrations of zinc sulfate. Etamon is a highly effective plant growth regulator and root formation stimulator of the new generation. The mitotic activity of apical meristem cells was assessed using cytological methods according to the generally accepted methodology. The study found that pre-sowing treatment of seeds in a 0.065% solution of Etamon led to a 37% increase in the mitotic index in the experiment with the maximum concentration (100 mM) of zinc sulfate. The germination of corn seeds in a pollutant environment contributed to the formation of a prophase-metaphase block and a decrease in the number of cells in anaphase and telophase. Under the action of the drug, the number of cells is redistributed towards the anaphase-telophase block. Thus, the drug Etamon stimulates the mitotic activity of cells in the apical meristem of corn roots under the action of various concentrations of zinc sulfate, with further enhancement of root growth processes and increased absorption capacity.

Keywords: Etamon, corn, mitotic index, cell division, zinc sulfate.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, technogenic pollution has become one of the most significant environmental factors determining the conditions of existence and evolution of all biota, including humans. The processes of natural development and functioning of ecosystems under the influence of anthropogenic impacts are determined both by the strength of the impact and the nature of the factors involved.

Environmental factors of anthropogenic origin alter soil properties, plant productivity, product quality, increase the number of salinated areas, and pollute the environment with heavy metals.

The problem of heavy metals is global in today's world. All heavy metals are highly toxic, migratory, and have carcinogenic and mutagenic properties [1, 2]. They not only inhibit plant growth and development, but also affect photosynthesis, respiration, water metabolism, and mineral nutrition, altering hormonal balance and membrane structure. [3,4]. Metals bind directly to amino acids and proteins, replace metal ions in enzymes, and regenerate free forms of oxygen, which is the basis of the toxic effect of metals [5–7]. Heavy metal ions, along with their general physiological toxicity, also exhibit genotoxic properties, damaging nuclear material and disrupting the phases of mitosis and cytokinesis [8–10].

Zinc is one of the most important essential trace elements, acting as a cofactor for a number of enzymes,

involved in photosynthesis and respiration, and protecting plants from oxidative stress [11]. However, the range of zinc concentrations that ensure optimal cellular metabolism and plant development is very narrow. It is believed that even a twofold excess can have a negative effect, while high zinc concentrations cause toxic syndromes (chlorosis and necrosis, inhibition of root and shoot growth), up to lethal effects [7, 12].

One of the most important ways to reduce the content of heavy metals in agricultural products is to treat plants with biologically active substances. The drug Etamon-dimethyl phosphoric acid (2-hydroxyethyl) ammonium is a highly effective plant growth regulator and root formation stimulator. It is used to accelerate root growth, improve seedling survival, restore plants after stress (drought, cold), and increase the yield of vegetable and fruit crops [13].

Growth consists of cell division and stretching, which leads to an increase in tissue mass and size and the formation of plant productivity. Growth disruption is one of the visible symptoms of the effects of various stress factors. Most of the substances that enter the plant are absorbed by the root system, which is why the root shows the initial reaction to their effects. Such exposure leads to disturbances in cell activity. Therefore, the aim of our research was to study the effect of the drug Etamon on the growth parameters of roots and the mitotic activity of cells in the apical meristem of germinating Sterling corn seeds against the background of zinc sulfate exposure.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sterling corn seeds and seedlings were used as research objects. The research was conducted in laboratory conditions. Corn seeds were selected according to their average size and treated for 20 minutes in a 1.5% solution of potassium permanganate for surface sterilization. The seeds were then washed with distilled water. Pre-sowing treatment of the seeds was carried out in a 0.065% solution of Etamon. The control part of the seeds was soaked in settled tap water. Zinc sulfate (e.c.c.) was used as a source of zinc ions. The seeds treated with the preparation were placed in cuvettes on filter paper and 200 ml of zinc sulfate solution of various concentrations (from 25 mM to 100 mM) was added. As a control, seeds were germinated in settled tap water and in zinc sulfate solutions of the same concentrations. The seeds were germinated in a DH 49 D thermostat in the dark at a temperature of +25 °C according to [14].

To determine the mitotic activity of corn seedling root meristem cells, the material was fixed in acetic alcohol (3:1) for 24 hours at +10 °C [15]. The fixed material was washed in 96% alcohol and stored in a 70% ethyl alcohol solution in a refrigerator. For cytological studies, the roots were stained with acetocarmin for 48 hours. Temporary pressure preparations of corn seedling root tips were prepared using a standard method [16]. Each experiment was performed in triplicate, analyzing at least 1000 cells. Mitotic and phase indices were calculated using standard formulas [16]. Statistical data processing was performed by calculating the arithmetic mean and standard error of the arithmetic mean [17].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The response of corn seedlings to zinc sulfate was consistent throughout the growth period and depended on the concentration of the metal in the growing medium. The results of the study are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Effect of Etamon on the length of the root system of corn plants against the background of zinc sulfate in dynamics ($\bar{x} \pm S_x$)

Experience options	Length of underground section, cm		
	7th day	14th day	21st day
Control	9.12±0.20	12.00 ± 0.09	15.16 ± 0.10
Control+ Etamon	9.92± 0.18	13.00± 0.25	16.20± 0.25
25 mM ZnSO ₄	13.21 ± 0.09	15.10 ± 0.28	19.011± 0.17
25 mM ZnSO ₄ + Etamon	14.11± 0.08	16.35± 0.13	19.07± 0,18
50 mM ZnSO ₄	8.41 ± 0.20	13.18 ± 0.16	15.22 ± 0.18
50 mM ZnSO ₄ + Etamon	12.41± 0.19	14.78± 0.10	17.14± 0.09
100 mM ZnSO ₄	6.70 ± 0.13	9.10 ± 0.10	12.48 ± 0.16
100 mM ZnSO ₄ + Etamon	10.01± 0.25	13.26± 0.11	16.49 ± 0.20

Note: the difference between the average values of the control and the experiment is significant at $P \leq 0.01$ for all variants

Under the influence of zinc sulfate at a concentration of 100 mM, the length of the root system of 7-day-old seedlings is inhibited by 26.5% compared to the control variant. In the experimental variant with pre-sowing treatment of corn seeds in a 0.065% solution of the Etamon preparation at this metal dose, the toxic effect is neutralized and the absolute values of the roots are 10 cm versus 9 cm in the control and 7 cm under the action of zinc sulfate (Table 1). This pattern persisted throughout the experiment, indicating the adaptogenic effect of the preparation. Simultaneously with the inhibition of root system growth by zinc sulfate, darkening of the root tips was observed, indicating necrosis of meristematic tissues. In the variants with pre-sowing treatment of seeds with Etamon, these symptoms were absent.

The data obtained indicate that Etamona increases the mitotic index of meristematic cells in corn roots in all variants of the experiment against the background of zinc sulfate action. Increasing zinc concentrations had a negative effect on the mitotic index, lowering it. At the maximum concentration of ZnSO₄, the mitotic index was 3.02%. In the same variant, but with pre-sowing treatment of seeds with the preparation, the value was 4.04%, increasing the mitotic index by 33%. Even at minimum zinc concentrations (25 mM ZnSO₄), the mitotic index decreases to 4.23%, while Etamona increases this indicator by 1.3 times. Thus, Etamona has a positive effect on cell division, contributing to an increase in the mitotic index.

Under the action of zinc sulfate, the ratio of individual phases of mitosis in meristematic cells of corn roots changes, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2

Effect of Etamon on phase index values of corn root cells in the apical meristem under the influence of zinc sulfate

Experiment options	Prophase	Metaphase	Anaphase	Telophase
Control	27.02±0.26	24.21±1.02	24.13±0.66	24.21±0.05
Control+ Etamon	26.32±1.12	25.25±0.16	26.11±0.61	26.01±0.33
25 mM ZnSO ₄	30.66±0.31	27.88±0.46	20.92±0.44	20.21±0.29
25 mM ZnSO ₄ + Etamon	29.62±0.55	22.31±0.29	25.68±1.09	23.09±0.44
50 mM ZnSO ₄	32.69±0.25	28.09±0.48	21.91±0.43	17.19±0.25
50 mM ZnSO ₄ + Etamon	29.79±0.57	21.38±0.31	26.68±1.12	23.09±0.40
100 mM ZnSO ₄	27.23±0.75	50.47±1.18	17.67±0.38	13.91±0.39
100 mM ZnSO ₄ + Etamon	30.69±0.90	30.18±0.89	8.69±0.51	20.18±0.40

Note: the difference between the average values of the control and the experiment is significant at $P \leq 0.01$ for all variants

At the maximum zinc concentration (100 mM ZnSO₄), the number of cells in metaphase increases sharply, the metaphase index is 52% and differs from the control by a factor of 2. In the variant with pre-sowing treatment of seeds with Etamona, the metaphase index decreases by 20%, and the number of cells in telophase increases by an average of 6.8%. At the minimum concentration of heavy metal, the maximum number of cells are in prophase and metaphase. In this variant of the experiment, Etamona did not have a significant effect on the phase indices of meristematic cells, and the anaphase index increased by 5%. At a zinc sulfate concentration of 50 mM, the maximum number of cells are in prophase (33%), and the minimum is in telophase (17%), whereas under the influence of the drug, the number of cells is redistributed across the phases of mitosis: the anaphase and telophase indices increase, and the metaphase index decrease.

In this experiment, Etamona did not have a significant effect on the phase indices of meristematic cells, with a 5% increase in the anaphase index. At a zinc sulfate concentration of 50 mM, the maximum number of cells is in prophase (33%), and the minimum is in telophase (17%), whereas under the influence of the drug, the number of cells is redistributed across the phases of mitosis—the anaphase and telophase indices increase, and the metaphase index decreases. In all variants of the experiment, under the influence of the drug Etamon, there is an increase in the percentage of anaphases and telophases. The increase in the number of cells in metaphase at the maximum concentration of metal in the corn seed growth medium may be due to the binding of zinc to the sulfhydryl groups of the mitotic apparatus [18, 19], resulting in their oxidation, as heavy metals enhance lipid peroxidation.

CONCLUSION

The studies conducted showed that as the concentration of zinc sulfate increases, the mitotic index of cells in the apical meristem of corn roots decreases, resulting in inhibition of root system growth as a whole. As the zinc concentration in the solution increased, a prophase-metaphase block was observed with a decrease in the duration of anaphase and telophase. The highest concentration of the pollutant in the medium caused a sharp increase in the percentage of cells in the

metaphase stage, which significantly reduced the number of cells in the anaphase and telophase stages. Treatment of seeds with Etamona levelled the ratio of cells in different phases of mitosis, which contributed to an increase in the linear parameters of the root system.

References

1. Bashmakov D.I., Lukatkin A.S. Ecological and physiological aspects of heavy metal accumulation and distribution in higher plants. Saransk: Mordovia University Press, 2009. 236 p.
2. Seregin I. V., Ivanov V. B. Physiological aspects of the toxic effects of cadmium and lead on higher plants. // *Plant Physiology*. – 2001. – Vol. 48. – P. 606–630.
3. Meharg A. A. 2005. Mechanisms of plant resistance to metal and metalloids ions and potential biotechnological applications. // *Plant Soil*. – 274. – P. 163–174.
4. Clemens S. Toxic metal accumulation, responses to exposure and mechanisms of tolerance in plants. // *Biochimie*. – 2006. – 88. – P. 1707–1719.
5. Evseeva T. I., Belykh E. S., Maistrenko T. A. Patterns of induction of cytogenetic effects in plants under the action of heavy metals. // *Bulletin of the Institute of Biology, Komi Scientific Center, Ural Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences*. – 2005. – Vol. 87, No. 1. – P. 4–13.
6. Ivanov V. B., Bystrova E. I., Seregin I. V. Comparison of the effect of heavy metals on root growth in connection with the problem of specificity and selectivity of their action. // *Plant Physiology*. – 2003. – Vol. 50. – P. 445–454.
7. Huseynov K. G., Dzhililov F. S., Koshkin E. I., Andreeva I. V., Huseynov G. G. The impact of global climate change on the productivity and resistance of agricultural crops to stressors. // *Agrochemistry*. 2019. No. 12. P. 83–96.
8. Gazieva A.S., Fathullaeva M., Kolesnik S.V., Umarov U.A. Synthesis of biologically active substances based on coordination compounds of copper (II) with acetylacetone and salicylic acid. // *International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation*, 2020. V. 24 - No. 8, p. 6504-6511.

9. Dovgalyuk L.I., Kalinyak T.B., Blum Ya.B. Cytogenetic effects of toxic metal salts in cells of the apical meristem of *Allium cepa* L. seedlings. // *Cytology and Genetics*. – 2001. – Vol. 35, No. 2. – P. 3–9.
10. Kozhevnikova A. D., Seregin I. V. et al. The effect of lead, nickel, and strontium nitrates on the division and elongation of corn root cells. // *Plant Physiology*. – 2009. – Vol. 56. – P. 268–278.
11. Guidelines for the use of vitamins and trace elements in medical practice. Arnebia LLC Part I. 2019. pp. 82–83.
12. Ignatov A. N., Koshkin E. I., Andreeva I. V., Huseynov G. G. The impact of global climate change on phytopathogens and the development of plant diseases. 2020. 250 p.
13. The multifunctionality of brassinosteroids. Collection of scientific papers. Moscow: NEST M, 2007. – 360 p.
14. GOST 12038–84. Seeds of agricultural crops. Methods for determining germination. Moscow: Interstate Standard: Standards Publishing House, 2011. – 29 p.
15. Sobchuk N. A., Chmeleva S. I. The effect of pre-sowing treatment with zircon on the mitotic activity of the apical meristem of corn roots. // *Scientific Notes of the V. I. Vernadsky Crimean Federal University. Series "Biology, Chemistry,"* 2015 – Volume 1 (67), No. 1. – Pp. 107–114.
16. Aliyeva A. K., Kubalova L. M. The biological role of chemical elements depending on their position in Mendeleev's periodic table. *Modern Science-Intensive Technologies*. 2014, No. 7-2, p. 83.
17. Protasov K.V. *Statistical Analysis of Experimental Data*. Moscow: Mir. 2005. – 232 p.
18. Ruggiero M. A., Gordon D. P., Orrell T. M., Bailly N., Bourgoin T., Brusca R. C., Cavalier-Smith T., Guiry M. D., Kirk P. M. A Higher Level Classification of All Living Organisms. // *PLOS ONE Editors PLoS*, 2015. Vol. 10, P.4-11.
19. Katashov D. A., Khryanin V. N. The effect of phytohormones and sodium selenate on the mitotic activity of apical meristems of rapeseed seedlings. // *News of Higher Educational Institutions. Volga Region. Natural Sciences*. – 2013. – No. 2 (2). – P. 49–54.